

THE METHODS TO INCREASE THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE ATMOSPHERE OF DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *Special attention is paid to the fact that solving existing unemployment problems in our country and further increasing the level of employment of the population is the main foundation of the country's development.*

Keywords: *digital economy, population employment, unemployment, digital technologies, labor market, IT sector, information and digital literacy.*

Introduction

In the current conditions of socio-economic development related to the implementation of economic reforms in our country, one of the priority tasks is to develop the goals and objectives of the population employment policy in the development of the economy. The employment of the population includes various forms and directions of labor activity related to the quality of modern life, creating conditions for the development of human capital and ensuring the transition of the division of labor to a higher level.

Several changes in employment in the labor market is happening. This is mostly information and communication technologies with the digital revolution caused by the development and advancement of science directly related. This revolution is affecting the labor market and globalization through digitalization of all sectors and industries. At the moment, the gradual disappearance of a number of professions, together with the increase in the number of unemployed people, are creating new modern professions and jobs, and with the help of effective use of digital and information technologies, many facilities are being created to solve unemployment problems.

Labor in countries with a highly developed digital economy a large part of its resources is mainly used in the field of digital technologies, i.e. IT. In particular, activity in this field in the USA in 2020

the number of qualified specialists is 2 million 760 thousand, in electronic business 21 million were employed. These areas are the country's dense interior. The share of products has also increased significantly, this sector is 5.5% and electronic business accounted for 12.8%. The digital economy is expected to bring about changes in more than half of the existing industries. The rate of growth of the digital economy in the world is almost 20% per year.

Methodology

The establishment of the digital economy is not only the result of scientific and technical progress or the natural evolution of society, but it is also related to the gradual implementation of "digitalization" programs under state management by the "leading" countries in the world economy. Such countries are primarily focusing on the digitalization of the labor market, because the digitalization of the economy determines the quantitative demand for labor force and regulates the supply and demand for it. According to expert agencies in the world, as a result of the

"digitalization" of jobs, 47% of jobs will be occupied by computer programs and robots. Also, in developed countries, as a result of digital technologies and robotization, 5 million people will be born in the next five years. jobs will disappear. Such a situation creates a unique socio-economic tension in the labor market. We can include the following in the list of such negative situations:

- reduction of jobs, displacement of live labor by machines and robots;
- increasing digital divide between internet-person and non-internet-person;
- increase in technological unemployment as a result of increasing automation, robotization, introduction of artificial intelligence system;
- of social guarantees for workers and employees, reduction of the social protection system;
- decrease in labor market, labor force demand capacity;
- of labor market forecasting and digitization, etc.

But along with the negatives recognized above, there are also positive aspects of digitization, which include:

- increasing labor productivity, reducing working hours;
- uniform increase of wages of highly skilled and low skilled workers;
- increasing the qualification and level of qualifications of personnel as a result of the increase in the demand for highly qualified labor;
- of new jobs with good working conditions, emergence of new professions;
- increasing job flexibility, expanding non-standard employment and reducing transaction costs in the labor market based on it;
- of time spent searching for a job, etc.

At present, researchers have different views on the impact of digitization of the economy on the labor market, and they distinguish all aspects of this process for the labor market as mentioned above. Expressions of the Keynesian direction of modern economic theory paid more attention to the interdependence and influence of labor and technology, employment and investment activity by economic dynamics. In particular, J.M.Keynes recognized in his theory that the new industrial revolution, i.e., the expansion of mechanized production, will lead to an increase in the widespread use of technological unemployment. K.Schwab, Florian A.Smith, representatives of this direction, in their works focused on revealing the features of the digitized labor market as a separate segment of the digital economy, that the factor representing the technological change of production and labor is information and communication technologies.

Results and analysis

Creation of new stable jobs, employment of the population, especially young people and women, increasing their competitiveness and professional level in the labor market is one of the most urgent and priority tasks that are being carried out in our country. We know that the majority of the population (60 percent of the population under 30 years old) is young. On April 20 of this year, President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev announced "Additional measures to support the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection, and the meaningful organization of their free time." on" Decree PF-6208 was signed. According to the decree, in order to increase employment among young people, a system of providing consumer loans for the purchase of computers in the amount of no more than 25 times the amount of the basic calculation for young people who successfully completed training courses and received a certificate in the project "One million programmers" was established. It is intended to be carried out.

However, it is not correct to say that the possibilities of the digital economy and the creation of new labor market mechanisms in increasing the level of employment of the population can completely solve the problem in this area. Because there are different segments of the population that need employment in the labor market, mainly young people, persons with disabilities and women can be cited as an example of the labor market segment. According to the analysis of statistical data, about 800,000 people with disabilities live in the Republic of Uzbekistan. 8.5% of them are disabled of group I, 71% of disabled of group II and 20.5% of disabled of group III. 97,000 of them are children under the age of 16. The number of employees is about 34,000. At the same time, people with the most severe form of disability (group I disabled) make up 3.5 percent. At the same time, employment of people with disabilities remains relevant. It is necessary to determine the economic and social efficiency of the measures aimed at ensuring the employment of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan, to clarify the legal framework and institutional mechanisms that ensure the employment of this group of citizens, and to develop proposals for increasing the efficiency of the current system. Equipping and appropriate adaptation of the workplace is organized at the expense of the employer in accordance with the legislation of most countries, including the USA and Great Britain. In many countries, if jobs are created in excess of the quota, the employer can receive compensation from the state budget. In most cases, people with disabilities cannot perform activities while visiting the workplace due to their limited capabilities during the work process. Therefore, it is necessary to encourage the creation of "virtual" workplaces that allow them to work remotely. The average unemployment rate in Uzbekistan is 9.3% of the total economically active population. In the case of women, the figure is 13 percent, which means that on average there are around 1 million unemployed women in Uzbekistan. In general, the supply of labor force in Uzbekistan is quite high, and the share of the economically active population (employed and job-seeking population) of the total number of labor resources reaches 71.0%. From the point of view of further reforming the employment and labor market situation, approximately 47.0% of the socially active population are women, 14.0% are young people under the age of 25, and 14.0% are people on the verge of retirement and of retirement age. it is important to get Despite the creation of all social and legal conditions for increasing the employment of women in our country, it does not meet the requirements of today's modern pace of economic development in this area. To improve this situation, it is necessary to go beyond gender issues, because most of them arise from the general problems of the formation and development of the labor market in the context of innovative reforms, and these problems have an impact on the level of employment of the population, especially women. The development of information technologies expands the types of professions, creates jobs for women and leads them to expand the fields of employment. Also, it is very important to support women in remote districts in the development of digital skills and entrepreneurial activities in the field of digital business, in our opinion, it is important to increase digital literacy, create electronic platforms for women entrepreneurs in remote districts, cheap internet service packages, etc.

According to official data, in 2019, the highest share of employed women in total employment in our Republic was in Tashkent city (46.7%), Navoi (45.6%), Bukhara (45%) and Fergana (44.2%) According to regions, the highest percentage of employed men is Surkhandarya (65.1%), Kashkadarya (61.9%), Samarkand (61.2%), Jizzakh (60.4%) and Syrdarya (60.0%) are accounted for by regions.

On the contrary, Surkhandarya (34.9%) and Kashkadarya have the lowest share of employed women (38.1%), Samarkand (38.8%) and Jizzakh (39.6%) regions, while the lowest percentage of employed men is in Tashkent city (53.3%), Navoi (54.4%), Bukhara (55%), and Fergana (55.8%) regions (Fig. 1). The number of people employed in the formal sector of the economy State statistics Committee, the State Tax Committee and the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations determined on the basis of information.

Figure 1. Distribution of items by gender in the cross-section of regions

Labor resources in Uzbekistan as of January 1, 2022 are 19.1 million. people, the economically active population is 14.8 million. people, total employment 13.2 mln. people, of which 5.7 million in the official sector of the economy. people (43.3%), 5.6 million in the informal sector of the economy. people (42.8%), 1.6 million people in need of employment. people (10.5%) and those who went to work abroad - 1.8 million. organized a person. The new version of the Law "On Employment of the Population" of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in 2020 and became a law with direct effect. It reflects the main principles of the state in the field of employment and is based on modern labor law norms. In particular, new means of regulating the labor market, in particular, encouraging entrepreneurship, self-employment, vocational training of the unemployed, improving their skills, taking into account the length of service, paying unemployment benefits, and placing them in work. agencies, citizens working temporarily outside the republic, and other important issues received.

Taking into account that the development of information technology plays an important role in the development and expansion of remote employment, which is one of the flexible forms of employment, remote employment prevents informal employment, formalization of income and especially when there is no job in the area of residence. Being officially remotely employed allows you to realize your skills and earn an income.

- working time flexibility in remote employment provides convenience for both employees and customers. At the same time, it allows to reduce additional costs. In this case, not only the area of the workplace is saved, but also the amount of electricity costs, administrative costs directed to control, transport costs in some enterprises and various subsidies (holidays, maternity leave) and other similar costs are saved;

- organization of home labor, in addition to technical means, also requires special management personnel who manage and regulate the activities of employees who perform labor activities at home and directly on the territory of the enterprise, which, in turn, requires additional

investments for training and training of these personnel. it is necessary to pay attention to education;

- in order to evaluate the modern forms of employment at the national level and to draw appropriate conclusions, it is appropriate to keep the number of employees in home work, remote employees, independent employees;

Discussion

Taking into account that the development of home work, in particular remote work, is a promising task in the near future due to information technologies and innovative development, social support for employees who perform work at home, ensuring working conditions and forming and improving the legal framework in this direction must 33.3 billion dollars to the economy of Uzbekistan in 2017-2020. As a result of foreign investments, including foreign direct investments of 22.7 billion dollars, stable new jobs are being created and growing in our country. As a result, 339.4 thousand new jobs were created in 2016, 389.3 thousand in 2017, 372.1 thousand in 2018, 388.5 thousand in 2019, and 427.8 thousand in 2020. Ensuring effective labor mobility of human resources within the country is important in ensuring employment of the population. In order to ensure decent and formal employment of the population, the "Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the promotion of population employment in 2021-2030" was developed. Target indicators and indicators achieved as a result of the implementation of this strategy in the field of development in the period until 2030. National goals and objectives serve sustainable and comprehensive economic growth based on increasing effective and decent employment. The number of employed people in our republic in 2021 is 13.2 million. 5.7 million people (43.3%) were in the formal sector of the economy.

According to the results of the analysis, by 2030, the population in the republic will increase by 20.7% or 7017.9 thousand people compared to 2020, labor resources by 21.9% or 4192.1 thousand people, employed population by 16% or 2125.5 per person is expected to increase and the share of informal workers will decrease to 20%. These indicators increase the employed population by an average of 1.15% per year during the perspective period and are wide as a result of the implementation of comprehensive comprehensive measures, the number of informal workers decreases by an average of 5% per year.

Main indicators of the labor market (annual average)

Indicators	2000y	2010y	2015y	2019y	2020y
<i>Labor resources, thousand people</i>	12594,0	16504,2	17663,1	18949,0	19142,3
<i>Economically active population, thousand people</i>	9018,4	12286,6	12850,1	14876,4	14797,9
<i>Level of economic activity of the population, %</i>	72,3	70,7	70,0	78,5	77,3
<i>Average annual number of jobs in the economy, thousand people</i>	8983,0	11628,4	12223,8	13541,1	13239,6
<i>Occupancy 0%</i>	72,0	66,9	66,6	67,4	68,3
<i>Number of unemployed, thousand people</i>	658,2	658,2	626,3	1335,3	1558,3

<i>The unemployment rate is at 0%</i>	5,4	5,4	4,9	9,0	10,5
<i>Economically inactive population, thousand people</i>	3575,6	4439,4	4714,2	4072,6	4344,4
<i>Level of economic inactivity (inaction), %</i>	27,7	25,5	25,7	21,5	22,7

In modern times, non-standard forms of employment, including the growth of self-employment of the population, are one of the characteristics of the flexibility of the labor market. For example, in the European Union, employees employed in non-standard forms of employment make up almost 40% of total employment, including almost 50% in the Netherlands. According to the ILO, the share of self-employed people in the total employment in the world is 42.5 percent. For example, in the European Union countries and the USA, they provide a wide range of services, more than 400 activities (entrepreneurial, social, realtor, brokerage, consulting services, advertising, retail, etc.) A number of useful opportunities can be obtained by doing 'ib. It should be noted that due to the impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the global economic and financial crisis, in 2020 compared to 2019, the employment rate increased slightly, despite the increase in the unemployment rate as a result of the decrease in the number of economically active population and the increase in the number of inactive population. This was caused by the implementation of measures aimed at supporting the population and entrepreneurship. In particular, in 2020, 493,000 citizens were employed, including 96,000 members of poor families included in the "iron register". 131,200 unemployed people were involved in paid public works. The number of people employed in peasant and private estates increased by 201,100 people. As a result, it was possible to prevent social threats to some extent.

In the conditions of the digital economy, it is necessary to take into account the fact that digital technologies, in turn, have a positive effect on the labor market. Through this, researches on the impact on the labor market have been conducted. During the last 15 years, the development of the Internet has lost 500,000 jobs that do not require high skills in the world, and 1.2 million new, high digital technologies have been created in this period. shows that jobs have been created.

Digital technologies lead to the creation of professions and specialties that did not exist in the labor market before. In particular, these include digital marketing, crowdsourcing, on-demand professional services, web marketer, ergonomist, web designer, contextual advertising manager, web developer. Currently, Internet technologies are increasingly used in the performance of labor functions in companies of developed countries. For example, in Germany, 80 percent of employees have mastered digital technologies and have high digital literacy. One of the advantages of this use is that using these technologies, large volumes of information can be processed in a short time. As a result of this, it is possible to find a job in the shortest possible time, to engage in work directly (online) regardless of time and place, and to earn additional income. In addition to the labor process, online workplaces serve to develop employment and stabilize the labor market by attracting disabled people, women engaged in raising children, and students. At the same time, the population of regions with a surplus of labor force will have the opportunity to work in other places, including with employers of foreign countries, on the basis of contracts.

In addition to these reforms, the following measures will be implemented in order to increase the level of effective employment of the able-bodied population in the digital economy in our country:

Improving the labor market based on the requirements of the time;

To improve the conjuncture in the labor market by regularly improving the skills of the able-bodied population in new professions;

Creating a competitive environment between employment services of the population;
preservation of existing jobs along with digitization of industries and networks;

Proportionately increase the skills of workers in the automation of production and service industries;

the system of training qualified employees and specialists, taking into account the priorities of socio-economic development strategies;

Creation of additional jobs on the basis of organization of training courses for new professions in order to eliminate the problem of unemployment to a certain extent.

In conclusion, we can say that in the conditions of the transition to the digital economy, the directions of ensuring the employment of the population have also improved to a certain extent. as well as lower prices or increased demand for technology-based products and services due to new markets, customer groups or territories.

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